

Reflection of Teacher Educator's Professionalism on Prospective Teachers

Asma Khizar Khizar	Ph.D. Scholar, Department of Education, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.
Muhammad Nadeem Anwar	Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan. Email: nadeem.anwar@uos.edu.pk
Mushtaq Ahmad Malik	Assistant Professor, Department of Education, University of Sargodha, Punjab, Pakistan.

Abstract

Reflection of teacher's own professionalism matters so the present study aimed to evaluate the reflection of teacher educator's professionalism on their students. The survey was conducted to collect data by using two self-developed questionnaires one for teacher educators and others for prospective teachers. A sample of 155 teacher educators and 200 prospective teachers participated in this study randomly selected from one general university of Islamabad and seven universities of Punjab province. Analyses revealed that prospective teachers were highly reflecting professional attitude, professional practice and professional confidence while less professional commitment, professional ethics, and professional knowledge and competence. Teacher educators showed high level of professional commitment, professional leadership and supportive culture whereas less professional practice, professional ethics and professional knowledge and competence. Nevertheless, the prospective teachers were not properly acquiring teacher educator's professionalism. Findings may be used in teacher education programs to enhance professionalism through organization of continuous professional development practices.

Key Words

Teacher Professionalism,
Reflection, Teacher
Educators, Prospective
Teachers, Teacher
Education programs

Introduction

Research evidence showed that the quality of teachers cannot be orchestrated without a strong teacher education system (Anwar, Yousuf, & Sarwar, 2008). A teacher education system that produces professionally fit human capital is the output of quality teaching and learning; therefore to compete in the evolution of digital technology, the education sector should be in concordance with the 21st-century advancement (Dali, Burgess, & Lee, 2018).

According to the explication of Kafu (2003) the importance of teacher education has been renowned in human life since ages, for example Lucas (1968) explained it as basic pillar of education system and mode to protect and transmit culture moreover, moral, social, political economics destiny of all societies is determined by teachers. Hence teaching is holy profession and its obligation of teachers to follow the divine mandate of teaching to cultivate its generation (Ogunyinka, Okeke, & Adedoyin, 2015).

It is evidence-based conclusion that among all educational resources, teachers' professionalism is the main contributor to teaching-learning process (Darling-Hammond, 2006). Moreover, professionalism seems to be emerging a key variable when talking about quality of teachers (Hill-Sakurai et al. 2008). A plethora of researches indicates that teachers with high-professionalism seemed to show more positive professional job attitudes, professional satisfaction, confidence, leadership, good spirit, and less disengagement (Townsend & Bates, 2007).

As a result of human development initiative and evolution, skilled teachers are increasing in different societies hence teachers are expected to polish professional competence and develop professionalism among students every day (Kramer, 2003).

The definition of professionalism involves professional behavior to fulfill the needs of specific disciplines. Ivanova (2019) expressed professionalism as institutionally prescribed responsibility also known as managerial approach of professionalism which personifies the views of teaching organizations, education regulatory bodies i.e. ministries, school heads, means to pinpoint what teachers are expected to know and what is quality of teaching. Such specifications are likely to differ from country to country and even public to private educational organizations. Another aspect of

professionalism referred as independent professionalism, which means teachers' own views of teaching and the processes by which teachers engage in reflection on their own values, beliefs, and practices.

In literature professional behavior of teachers means the portray of skills, disposition, and professional knowledge, however teacher's professionalism is complex and it's hard to define (Caspersen, 2013). The teaching profession entails a specific knowledge acquired from academic as well as real-world experience. The teaching profession is a profession that is centered on some requirements as well as professional standards. At a basic level a professional person someone who gets salary to teach while at higher level teacher is a person who demonstrates best in profession and sets higher standards for best practices. For example Aghaalkhani and Maftoon (2018) have opined that professional teacher has mastery over subject and fulfill intellectual demands of discipline. The teacher can analyses needs of the students and they are responsible for it. Teachers know and maintain standard of teaching and feel accountable to meet needs of the students. Hence this definition elaborates professional level of teaching and reveals that it a complex responsibility.

In Pakistan, teacher education programs emphasize implementation of National Professional Standards for Teachers (NPSTs) which are based on three vital elements for developing professionalism. These elements are contributing to prepare professional teachers having knowledge, skills, and dispositions. Knowledge means students are equipped with information that can be applied in real life while skills deal with variety of pedagogy to develop interest of the students and make learning memorable whereas disposition addresses what is viewed as professionalism (Shami, 2009).

Professionalism exemplifies the attributes and desired behaviors toward which teachers aspire while serving their students. Teacher professionalism received attention in current years, primarily because of the low enrollment rate, low quality of teaching, decrease success rate in the terminal examination, which is often related to unprofessional behavior. Traditionally, learners have been learned professional values and behaviors from teachers. The presence of teacher educators as role models is crucial in inspiring professionalism among pupil students. Reflection is a fundamental construct that is appropriate for understanding as well as development of professionalism among learners (Horlick, Masterton, & Kalet, 2006). Professionalism is actually the skill to imitate deliberately and systematically on one's experiences. According to Leung and Yuen (2009) reflection involves looking at what shape have prospective students gained after passing through teaching experiences in an organized and systematic way (Leung & Yuen, 2009).

Literature Review

Due to change in social, political a historical scenario the conception of teacher's professionalism has multiple meanings that have been emerged and developed over time (Hilferty, 2008). This concept is difficult to define as it has different senses. It may be defined, for example, as activity for which teachers are being paid, moreover it may be used to define occupation status with reference to respectability (Kennedy, 2007). Professionalism in business is entirely related to success (Tichenor & Tichenor, 2005). Demirkasımoğlu (2010) focused professionalism on criteria such as a public service, based on theoretical and practical expertise, ethical dimensions with reference to code of conduct, for discipline and recruitment it needs regulations and organization, and individual autonomy (independent judgment) to become professional practitioners. WU and GAO (2012) in respect of Victorian Institute of Teaching's mentioned that reflection of teachers serving in teacher education institutions could be seen through Standards for Graduating Teachers, which coupled the theme (i) pedagogical models from practice and knowledge of recent learning theories, (ii) awareness of key concept, development and structure in area content, (iii) Integration of students understanding and learning among different content areas, (iv) awareness about assessment, recording and reporting tools of students learning and sharing it with all stakeholders, and (v) understanding and practice of equity among students. Numerous evidences indicated that reflection of teacher educators can be determine with the features of professionalism like professional autonomy, connection in the entering to the profession, observation of ethical codes, membership with professional societies, integrity and dedication, public accountability, practice-based strong academic knowledge, development of knowledge with the help of academic/action research and self-study, lifelong-learning, collaboration with all stakeholders, promote novelty, and finally, assurance to understand the educational matters.

When qualities of individual professionals are defined with the help of these characteristics, a conceptual framework with reference to skills, knowledge, and dispositions may be used to analyses teacher education's curriculum. Professionalism and its dispositions can be explicated overtly and covertly. Overtly, it explains programmatic expectations to the new entrants and how these expectations will be fulfilled with the help of curriculum. Seifert (1999) offered that it is lifelong challenge to become a professional; moreover also explained professionalism is tilted towards process than outcome. It is way of dealing with problems of new students and their solution.

Stronge, Tucker, and Hindman (2004) states that some researchers show that teacher effectiveness can be determined by student's achievement; while other highlights rating from supervisor as high performance while others depend on opinion from administrator, students, and willing stakeholders. The issue is not to manage single or different definitions of professionalism rather it is aimed to develop behavior parameters and traits fostered among teachers. Further, literature describes the complexities of teachers' professionalism and these descriptions are mostly theoretical in nature rather than empirical research. The purpose of our exploratory study was to begin an empirical examination reflection of teacher educator's professionalism with reference to prospective teachers. Teacher's professionalism can be judged from his/her personality, knowledge, communication and management skills (Chek & Pandey, 2016).

Literature indicated that researches on reflection of teachers were based on several indicators, however within Pakistani context eleven indicators were selected that indicates the state or level of professionalism. It is used to show visually the condition of a professionalism construct.

The development of professionalism among teachers explicitly is a growing construct in teacher education. For well-growing professionalism among teachers Higher Education Commission with the collaboration of international agencies, for example, World Bank, UNICEF, CIDA, UNESCO, etc. have established National Accreditation Council for Teacher Education and planned to phase out one year (B.Ed/M.Ed) and two years (MA-Education) teacher education programs till 2020. Instead of these, Higher Education Commission introduced four years programs. Two programs, for example B.S-Education and B.Ed-Honour have started in order to promote better professional development high professionalism among prospective teachers. At the heart of these programs is reflection; because reflection is to be considered a core skill for professional development and competence. A reflection is paying attention to the learners for their all-round development and better learning. It also indicates that how teacher teaches and select vibrant pedagogy. Teacher's reflection can make students be active in the classroom, participate in learning process and hands-on activities and at the same time embraces the 21st-century skills of learning. This is quite helpful in developing professionalism (Hatem, 2003). It is teacher's reflection that transforms his knowledge and experience into understanding and promoting higher degree of learning. Therefore, under the umbrella of above-mentioned indicators of professionalism to identify the level of professionalism among teacher educators as well as prospective teachers, and level of reflection of professionalism of teacher educators on their students i-e prospective teachers, the researchers have focused on following questions:

1. What is the level of professionalism among teacher educators?
2. What is the level of professionalism among students (prospective teachers) of BS-Education/B.Ed-Honour?
3. Is there a significant reflection of the professionalism of teacher educators on prospective teachers?

Methodology

This study was descriptive in nature which involved the only description of conditions about level of professionalism and determines the reflection of teacher educators on prospective teachers.

Sample and Sampling

This manuscript has involved stakeholders of general universities such as teacher educators and prospective teachers. The present study was inductive and descriptive in nature which involves only description of conditions, settings, and events. The cross-sectional survey has been conducted to collect data to measure behavior, attitude, and beliefs at a single point in time (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2000). The sample was drawn by using multistage random sampling technique. There were three public sector universities in Islamabad Capital Territory (ICT) and fifteen (15) in the province of Punjab who offered education as a discipline. Out of which 1 from Islamabad and 7 from Punjab universities were randomly selected. All faculty members from these eight universities were included as sample (n=155). However, from each university 25 prospective teachers of final semester of BS-Education/B. Ed-honor were taken conveniently (n=200).

Instrumentation

A set of two questionnaires were developed to measure the reflection of professionalism among prospective teachers, one for teacher educators and second for prospective teachers. Items were identified through a synthesis of literature review. Relevant indicators were identified and assembled into eleven factors in research tools such as professional satisfaction, professional commitment, professional attitude, professional ethics, professional practice, professional knowledge and competencies, professional human relation, supportive culture, professional leadership, professional growth, and confidence. In response categories the scaling of selected items has utilized a five-point rating scale i.e. fully, largely, moderately, poorly & not at all. A rating scale ranging from one to five corresponded to different categories in different sections of the instrument and reflect a continuum from agreement to disagreement in terms of fully agree to not at all agree respectively. For determining the reliability, pilot testing was carried out in two phases. In first phase questionnaires were discussed with Ph.D. scholars and experts in field of education. Data for pilot testing who were collected from respondents i-e prospective teachers and teacher educators, were requested to complete the research instrument and give suggestions regarding clarity of each item, clarity about the direction of each item, ranking of scale, and other relevant suggestions. Feedback from experts was recorded and suggested changes were made in the instruments. After pilot testing reliability coefficient Cronbach's alpha values were .95 and .97 respectively for teacher educator's questionnaire and prospective teacher's questionnaire respectively.

Analysis of Data

As it was a quantitative survey so both descriptive and inferential statistics were run by using SPSS. Description of scores with small indices involved in descriptive statistics and used in organizing, summarizing and simplifying the data. Whereas, inferential statistics helps to make generalization about population from selected sample (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2004). A significance level of $\alpha = .05$ was set a priority. The overall percentage of frequency distributions, means, standard deviations and regression were computed during analysis.

Table 1. Teachers Educators Opinion about Professionalism

Sr. #	Statement	Fully	Largely	Moderately	Poorly	Not at all	Mean	S D
1	Professional Satisfaction	12%	38%	39%	10%	1%	3.49	0.53
2	Professional Commitment	31%	42%	24%	3%	0%	4.01	0.55
3	Professional Attitude	17%	35%	34%	14%	0%	3.56	0.79
4	Professional Ethics	17%	31%	32%	19%	1%	3.44	0.77
5	Professional Practice	13%	33%	35%	18%	1%	3.38	0.76
6	Professional Knowledge and Competencies	16%	32%	31%	18%	3%	3.41	0.81
7	Professional Human Relations	14%	39%	40%	5%	2%	3.61	0.66
8	Supportive culture	11%	54%	26%	8%	1%	3.69	0.59
9	Professional Leadership	9%	55%	33%	3%	Nil	3.69	0.45
10	Professional Growth	14%	42%	29%	14%	1%	3.56	0.70
11	Professional Confidence	14%	43%	32%	10%	1%	3.60	0.72

Table 1 reflects that 50% of respondents fully or largely opined with favoring mean score 3.49 and SD=0.53 that teacher educators are professionally satisfied whereas 39% respondents were moderately satisfied. 73%

respondents with supportive mean score 4.01 and SD=0.55 expressed opinion as fully or largely in favor that teacher educators are professionally committed. 52% respondents fully or largely opined in support that professional attitude of teacher educators with favoring mean score 3.56 and SD=0.79 while 34% respondents opined moderately. Professional ethics of teacher educators were fully or largely opined by 48% respondents with favoring mean scores 3.44 and SD=0.77 whereas 32% respondents opined moderately. 46% respondents favoring mean score 3.38 and SD=0.76 fully or largely opined professional practice of teacher educators while 35% respondents opined in support moderately. Professional knowledge and competencies of teacher educators were fully or largely opined by 48% subjects with favoring mean score 3.41 and SD=0.81 whereas 31% respondents opined moderately. With favoring mean score 3.61 and SD=0.66, 53% respondents fully or largely opined to strengthen professional human relations of teacher educators whereas 40% respondents opined in favor moderately. 64% respondents' favoring mean score of 3.69 and SD=0.59 fully or largely indicate a supportive culture. Professional leadership was fully or largely opined by 64% respondents with favoring mean score 3.69 and SD=0.45 whereas 33% respondents opined moderately. With favoring mean score 3.56 and SD=0.70 professional growth of teachers educators were fully or largely opined by 56% respondents and 29% respondents opined moderately. Professional confidence was fully or largely opined by 57% respondents while 32% moderately opined in favor of favoring mean score 3.60 and SD=0.72.

Table 2. Level of Professionalism among Teacher Educator

Level of Professionalism	F (n=155)	%
Low (Mean < 3)	05	03
Moderate (Mean 3 to 3.99)	77	50
High (Mean ≥ 4)	73	47

The level of professionalism among teacher educators (Table 2) was found low that can be shown through the low percentage of responses i-e 3 and the Mean value was to be than 3. Responses of teacher educators 77(50%) indicated moderate level of professionalism because the mean value ranged from 3 to 3.99. Moreover, table showed professionalism of teacher educators' higher level as Mean ≥ 4 (47%).

Table 3. Prospective Teachers Opinion about Professionalism

Sr. #	Indicators	Fully	Largely	Moderately	Poorly	Not at All	Mean	S D
1	Professional Satisfaction	32%	26%	29%	10%	3%	3.77	0.38
2	Professional Commitment	37%	15%	20%	14%	14%	3.48	0.48
3	Professional Attitude	51%	30%	14%	3%	2%	4.25	0.50
4	Professional Ethics	46%	05%	12%	14%	23%	3.46	0.65
5	Professional Practice	56%	21%	13%	5%	5%	4.18	0.56
6	Professional Knowledge and Competencies	32%	23%	21%	5%	19%	3.44	0.61
7	Professional Human Relations	44%	18%	13%	5%	20%	3.60	0.49
8	Supportive Culture	49%	26%	16%	4%	5%	4.08	0.64
9	Professional Leadership	47%	24%	22%	4%	3%	4.08	0.53
10	Professional Growth	45%	18%	21%	6%	10%	3.79	0.60
11	Professional Confidence	63%	20%	13%	1%	3%	4.39	0.56

Table 3 reflects that 58% of respondents fully or largely supported professional satisfaction with favoring mean score 3.77 and SD=0.38 whereas 29% respondents moderately opined. With favoring mean score 3.48 and SD=0.48, 52% respondents fully or largely favored professional commitment. 81% respondents with supportive

mean score 4.25 and SD=0.50 fully or largely preferred professional attitude. 51% respondents fully or largely agreed with professional ethics with favoring mean score 3.46 and SD=0.65. The professional practice was fully or largely favored (77%) with supportive mean score 4.18 and SD=0.56. While 55% respondents fully or largely favored professional knowledge and competencies with favoring mean score 3.44 and SD=0.61. With favoring mean score 3.60 and SD=0.49, 62% respondents fully or largely favored professional human relations. With supportive mean score 4.08 and SD=0.64, 75% respondents fully or largely supported supportive culture. Professional leadership was fully or largely (71%) favored with supportive mean score 4.08 and SD=0.53. 63% respondents fully or largely favored professional growth with favored mean score 3.79 and SD=0.60. Professional confidence was fully or largely favored (83%) respondents with supportive mean score 4.39 and SD=0.56.

Table 4. Level of Professionalism among Prospective Teachers

Level of Professionalism	F (n=200)	%
Low (Mean < 3)	Nil	Nil
Moderate (Mean 3 to 3.99)	53	27
High (Mean ≥ 4)	147	73

The findings in the above table 4 explicated that prospective teachers' level of professionalism was found moderate (Frequency=53 i-e 27%), mean value was found within the rage of 3 to 3.99. Whereas, responses 147(73%) indicated high level of professionalism among prospective teachers because the mean was found greater than 4. However, no response was recorded in low level category.

Table 5. Reflection of Professionalism of Teacher Educators and Prospective Teachers

Model Summary				
Construct	R	R Square	F	Sig
	0.17 ^a	0.016	7.01	0.85

a=teacher educators level professionalism

Coefficients ^a					
Construct	Unstandardized Coefficients		Unstandardized Coefficients	T	Sig
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Construct	2.42	0.32		7.38	0.00
	0.09	0.19	0.55	2.26	0.85

a= prospective teachers level professionalism (students)

Table 5 shows the reflection of teacher educator's professionalism on prospective teachers (students of BS-Education/B. Ed-honor). The R square is 0.016 which means 1.6% reflection of teacher educator's professionalism was found on prospective teacher's professionalism. The B is 0.09 ($p=0.85$) this indicated that if 1 unit increase (high) in the level of professionalism will be caused 0.09 unit overall increase (high). In respect of reflection of professionalism, there is no significant relationship between the opinions of teacher educators and prospective teachers.

Conclusion & Discussion

This study was aimed to explore the reflection of teacher educator's professionalism on prospective teachers. It was found that prospective teachers were reflecting a high level of professionalism than their teacher (teacher educators). The majority of the prospective teachers showed high level of professionalism whereas half of the teacher educator showed high while half showed moderate level of professionalism. It may be inferred teacher educators observing their responsibility in letter and spirit and in the same context Hattie (2009) argued that teachers play an important role in the development and professional growth, and upbringing of their students. They are the ones who teach, judge and evaluate the future teachers, and their competence and abilities and skills affect the outcome of schooling. Apart from this according to Khan et al., (2016) students are to be considered a deep observer, they follow their teachers from all aspects. However, surprisingly, the researchers reached a conclusion that no significant reflection of the professionalism of teacher educators on prospective teachers was observed. Finding in terms of reflection is supported by a study conduct by (Swick, Szenas, Danoff, & Whitcomb, 1999) in which they discussed that teacher educator's professionalism is no considered sufficiently reflected on prospective teachers due to heterogeneity of

students, who admitted to teacher education institutions with different social, cultural, and socioeconomic backgrounds (Swick et al., 1999).

These research findings were reasoned out by (Ahmad, 2012) that teacher education had been influenced in Pakistan by multiple factors. Professional standards for teacher educators in universities were higher as compared to school leveled teachers. Moreover, it was highlighted that poor implementation of educational professional development policies and poor quality practices were the key factor for the unsatisfactory level of professionalism among teacher educators including lack of resources, lack of national vision, weaker political will, unrealistic financial input and poor coordination among higher education institutions. Ashraf et al. (2015) had also explicated the causes of low professionalism which rendered support. They indicated that poor infrastructure, lack of professional exposure and training, and low level of motivation low causes towards low professionalism. The professional development of teachers has multiple features that need more advanced studies for strengthening and putting into practice in teacher education programs. More efforts are needed to inculcate professional commitment, professional ethics and professional knowledge and competence among teacher educators for enhancing professionalism. Cruess (2006) mentioned regarding low level of professionalism in his study is context-specific nature of professionalism because in higher education institutions expectations from teacher educators were high and contextual factors, for example, social, resources, and technology have influenced professional development. So that professionalism is sensitive to context and there is no one-size-fits-all in respect of professionalism (Ho, Yu, Hirsh, Huang, & Yang, 2011). Teacher education programs may work for better professional practice, professional ethics and professional knowledge and competence of teacher educators. It may be recommended that teacher training in line with the professional standards for teacher educators may be revisited keeping professional standards set by the Higher Education Commission to ensure its effectiveness to develop professionalism.

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